

aldehyde is itself an inhibitor but the activity of the Schiff's bases cannot be accounted for the presence of this grouping alone, as the molar amount of cinnamic aldehyde present in the minimum bactericidal concentration of the different Schiff's bases is less than the minimum concentration of cinnamic aldehyde necessary for its bactericidal action against *E. typhosa* and *V. cholerae* (vide Table I).

Another characteristic noticed in the course of this investigation is that cinnamic aldehyde is more active against *cholerae* than against *typhosa*, and this characteristic is retained even when this is condensed with *p*-aminobenzoic acid. But its condensation product with 5-aminosalicylic acid is more potent against *E. typhosa*. This again raises the interesting question on the relationship of the growth factors of *E. typhosa* with aminobenzoic acid derivatives (cf. Raydon, *Brit. J. Exp. Path.*, 1948, 29, 48). *p*-Aminobenzoic acid does not appreciably function in the metabolism of *E. typhosa*, whereas the *ortho* compound has been shown to be utilised by the organism. Is then the amino group in the *meta* position in compound (V, R=III) playing a newer role? Further study in this direction is in progress. It may be recorded here that the different activity of the various drugs might be accounted for the difference in their degree of adsorption by the bacterial cell (cf. Julius and Winkler, *Ant. v. Leeuwenhoek*, 1941, 7, 25 and subsequent papers) as this might then inhibit the respiratory enzymes by interfering with the metabolism of *p*-aminobenzoic acid (cf. Sevag and co-workers, *J. Bact.*, 1942, 43, 447; 1945, 49, 71) at different rates. Under this hypothesis further investigations for the synthesis of this type of compounds with suitable unsaturated linkage that may interfere with the metabolism of the pathogenic organism, may be of considerable interest from therapeutic point of view, particularly as the compound (V, R=III) does not undergo any change and only up to 20% when kept at 37.5° for 3½ hours in contact with alkali solution (p_H 7.8-8.0) and with 0.4% hydrochloric acid respectively.

TABLE I

No.	Compound,	<i>E. typhosa</i>			<i>V. cholerae</i>		
		(a).	(b).	(c).	(a).	(b)	(c)
1	Cinnamic aldehyde	2.32	2.32	...	1.31	1.31	...
2.	Cinnamylidene sulphathiazole (V, R=I)	2.98	1.16	...	2.79	1.09	...
3.	Do bisulphite compound	...	...	>4	...	...	>4
4.	Sulphathiazole (I)	...	...	>0.5	...	...	<1.6
5.	Cinnamylidene sulphone compound (V, R=II) —	3.75	1.74	...	2.34	1.04	...
6.	Do bisulphite compound	..	...	>5	...	...	>5
7.	Aminophenylmethylsulphone (II)	...	...	>5	...	...	>5
8.	Cinnamylidene compound from 5-aminosalicylic acid (V, R=III)	2.35	1.16	...	2.2	1.09	...
9.	5-Aminosalicylic acid (III)	...	...	>5	...	...	>5
10.	Cinnamylidene compound from <i>p</i> -aminobenzoic acid (V, R=IV)	3.31	1.74	...	2.07	1.09	...

Bactericidal Activity of Schiff's Bases and Compounds (vide Table I).—E. typhosa 901 'H' and *V. cholerae* Inaba 2812, 1 million cells in 5 c.c. were used. Period of incubation was as shown in the body of the paper. Figures under column (a) indicate mg. of compound per c.c. showing bactericidal activity at the lowest concentration against the organism tested; figures under column (b) indicate the molar amount of cinnamic aldehyde present in the Schiff's bases as shown under column (a); and figures under column (c) indicate the concentration of the parent compound bactericidal to the organism.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Schiff's Bases.—Cinnamic aldehyde, freshly distilled, was mixed with the amino compound in molecular proportion in alcoholic (95%) solution, and warmed on a water-bath. Soon crystals of the Schiff's bases separated out; these were filtered, washed with ether and dried. They were finally crystallised from the appropriate solvent and kept in a closed container. The characteristics have been recorded in Table II. The compounds are soluble in excess of acid and impart a colour to the solution.

Reaction with Sodium Bisulphite.—To Schiff's base obtained from sulphathiazole as well as from *p*-aminophenylmethylsulphone was treated with a freshly prepared solution of a molecular quantity of sodium bisulphite, made by passing sulphur dioxide gas into an aqueous solution of a molar amount of sodium carbonate. The mixture was gently warmed on a water-bath for a few minutes when an almost clear solution was obtained. This was left overnight. Next day the solution was filtered, concentrated on a water-bath, and finally precipitated by addition of alcohol. The bisulphite compound was redissolved in water, filtered and purified by reprecipitation with alcohol. The product was dried over calcium chloride in *vacuo*. Sulphathiazole compound has been described in Indian Patent No. 29253; the product from *p*-aminophenylmethylsulphone gave (Na, 9.39. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2NS$, 2 $NaHSO_3$ requires Na 9.33 per cent).

TABLE II

Schiff's bases with cinnamic aldehyde.

Base from	Nature.	Formula & M. W.	M. p.	Nitrogen	
				Calc.	Found.
Sulphathiazole (I)	Pale yellow needles; insoluble in ether but soluble in alcohol and acetone	$C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_3S_2$ (369)	Chars at about 210°	12.39%	12.43%
<i>p</i> -Aminophenylmethylsulphone (II)	Yellow shining plates; insoluble in ether and chloroform; soluble in acetone; crystallised from alcohol	$C_{16}H_{16}O_2NS$ (285)	178°	4.91	4.46
5-Aminosalicyclic acid (III)	Fine garnet-red crystals; insoluble in ether but soluble in alcohol, acetone and ethyl acetate	$C_{16}H_{13}O_3N$ (267)	186°	5.24	4.8
<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid (IV)	Shining yellow needles, soluble in ether and chloroform; crystallised from alcohol.	$C_{16}H_{13}O_2N$ (251)	154-55°	6.07	6.21

Bactericidal Activity.—In the course of this investigation *E. typhosus* "901" and *V. cholerae* Inaba^c 2812 were used as test organisms. The inoculum throughout was chosen as 1 million cells as checked by nephelometry and viable count, and suspensions of the organisms were always prepared from an 18 hours young cultures on nutrient agar in peptone water of p_H 7.8. The strains chosen were smooth and partially susceptible.

The serial dilutions of the stock preparations of the compounds made from their alkaline solution in cases of compounds Nos. 3, 4, 6, 8, 9 and 10 and from 5% gum acacia emulsion in cases of compounds Nos. 1, 2, 5 and 7 (vide Table I), were prepared on the results of the preliminary minimum inhibitory concentrations of the products obtained by the double plate technique. After sterilisation at 15 lbs. pressure for 20 minutes the tubes were inoculated with 1 million cells of the test organisms contained in 0.06 c.c. and incubated at 37.5° for 24 hours. In case of cinnamic aldehyde it was added straight to sterile media tubes. The contents (5 c.c. in each case) that showed no growth were transferred aseptically into fresh sterile 1% peptone water (p_H 7.8) in such aliquots as to obtain subminimal bacteriostatic concentrations (noticed at the end of 24 hours and in the preliminary investigation). These were again incubated at 37.5° for 100 hours and the lowest dilution showing no growth was taken as the minimum bactericidal concentration for the compound against the particular organism tested and as shown in Table I. The activity of the bisulphite compounds (3 and 6, Table I) and of (II) and (III) was studied by the agar plate method for obtaining comparative maximum inactive value.